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**MEDIA SUPPORT FOR THE PARLIAMENTARY
OPPOSITION IN POLAND AFTER 2015:
SELECTED EXAMPLES**

ABSTRACT

The analysis examined the phenomenon of media support for the parliamentary opposition in Poland after 2015, placing it in the broader context of changes in the media system and political polarisation. The considerations undertaken concern the classic understanding of the role of the media as the fourth estate in democracy, with particular emphasis on the importance of their independence, pluralism and journalistic responsibility as conditions for the proper functioning of the public sphere. At the same time, it is pointed out that after 2015, as a result of the change in power, there was a significant shift in the function of both public and private media towards political engagement, which weakened their neutrality and further deepened social divisions.

Keywords: *parliamentary opposition, media, Poland, United Right, media narratives*

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary media has an extremely important role in the political system of a country, from influencing various aspects of the functioning of democracy, through increasing political stability, to how citizens perceive the reality around us (including the political reality). From the point of view of state institutions, the media act as a regulator ensuring the transparency of those in power, significantly influencing the integration of society as a whole, while performing a number of functions including informational, educational, supervisory, mobilising and entertainment (Litwin, 2023, pp. 261-263).

A prerequisite for the proper existence and operation of the media in a democratic state governed by the rule of law is not only their freedom, but also their independence, covering fundamental issues of freedom of speech and the press, i.e. informing the public and freely expressing opinions without any restrictions or censorship by the state or the authorities. This applies in particular to criticism of those in power, towards whom the media assume the unequal status of the „fourth estate” (Bonikowska, 2009, pp. 18-19). It is difficult to disagree with Jerzy Jastrzębski’s (2007, p. 288) opinion that „the media, by their very nature, should remain independent observers and critics of the political scene, as well as organisers and hosts of free and open debate, i.e. representatives of public opinion. And since the public (society, the general citizenry) is the constitutional sovereign in a democracy, its voice, moderated and conveyed by the media, is to be the voice of the highest and primary authority, which during elections indirectly or directly appoints the next authorities and exercises control over them”.

This opinion closely correlates with media pluralism, i.e. not only the diversity of owners and the variety of information preventing the monopolisation of the media by political parties, pressure groups or those in power, but also the complete financial independence of the media from the state. Journalists practising this profession should be guided in their mission by specific standards of reliability, impartiality and objectivity, responsibility for the content they convey and its prior verification in order to avoid manipulation and misinformation (Szot, 2016, pp. 369-391).

The scientific objective of the article was to analyse the phenomenon of media support provided by selected media outlets in Poland to the political opposition after 2015. The aim of this article is to answer the research question: why and in what ways selected media outlets in Poland after 2015 increasingly assumed the role of actors supporting the parliamentary opposition in the political communication process. Instead of verifying a strictly formulated hypothesis, the analysis focuses on identifying mechanisms through which media narratives contributed to strengthening opposition actors and shaping public perceptions of political competition.

From a methodological perspective, the article employs qualitative discourse analysis focusing on selected examples of media coverage and political commentary. The analysis concentrates on interpretative frames, narrative structures and evaluative language used in journalistic materials referring to the ruling camp and the parliamentary

opposition. At the same time, the qualitative perspective is supplemented with available empirical data concerning media consumption and public trust in the media, which makes it possible to place the analysed narratives in a broader socio-political context.

THREE CATEGORIES OF OPPOSITION: POLITICAL, PARLIAMENTARY AND MEDIA

There is no doubt that political opposition is a permanent feature of the political system associated with the consolidation of power, especially within a democratic model of government, in which political parties and entities engage in political competition that allows for the redistribution of elites and those in power (Schumpeter, 1995, pp. 336-337 ; Kotarba, 2014, pp. 161-162). The opposition is an essential component of the political system, as by participating in political decision-making, it exercises its constitutional guarantees related to, among other things, the sovereignty of the nation, the separation of powers and political representation (Machelski, 2021, pp. 216-217). The existence of opposition is not only linked to the articulation of the interests of broad social groups, but also serves to ensure proper mechanisms for controlling the actions of those in power, thus enabling their ongoing monitoring, criticism and the proposal of alternative programmes. These activities serve to strengthen the democratic character of the state through constructive dialogue, and also ensure control over the process and quality of legislation (Łabędź, 2010, p. 10 ; Nocoń, 2001, p. 36-37).

Focusing on how political opposition is understood, particularly in the context of discussions in numerous scientific studies and analyses, we can distinguish two ways of approaching it: narrower (*sensu stricto*) and broader (*sensu largo*). In the first case, political opposition should be treated as an institution of the democratic system, constituting a counterbalance and alternative to those currently in power in terms of values and programmes (Krawczyk, 2000, p. 132 ; Łabędź, 2012, pp. 176-177).

In the second, which also takes into account opposition in non-democratic systems, the concept of opposition is enriched and broadened to include a framework that transcends democratic institutions. In this sense, the concept of political opposition should be understood as a set of actors (parties, social movements, organisations, groups), including attitudes and behaviours capable of articulating opposition to those in power and questioning the foundations of the political order. Regardless of the comments made here, however, political opposition should be treated as important from the point of view of the citizens themselves, because, due to the nature of the state, it is a vehicle for ideas and alternative values, and is also sometimes an expression of opposition to certain practices related to governing the country. and it also performs a number of functions (including control, opinion-forming and mobilisation), contributing to the better functioning of the democratic system.

Parliamentary opposition remained a special type of political opposition, treated in a narrower sense than political opposition – as described, among others, by

Eugeniusz Zwierzchowski (2001), who defined it as political groups or parliamentary factions which, for whatever reason, do not participate in the formation of the government, but are critical of it. Zwierzchowski, who described it as „political groups or parliamentary factions which, for whatever reason, do not participate in the formation of the government, are critical of its political programme and activities, and develop their own alternative programme and personnel in order to take over and exercise power within the framework of constitutionally established rules” (Zwierzchowski, 2001, p. 11). According to the adopted definition, it should be noted that the parliamentary opposition consisted of those MPs and Senators who competed with politicians in power on the basis of constitutional, statutory and regulatory mechanisms of political practice.

In the further part of these considerations, it was necessary to refer to one of the typologies of political opposition proposed by Krzysztof Pałeczki (2001, p. 17), who distinguished, among others, regime opposition and civic opposition. The first of these types was systemic in nature, i.e. the entities included in it participated both in the competition for power and in its exercise. In addition, they participated in decision-making processes, which was particularly evident in the case of the parliamentary opposition. The civic opposition, on the other hand, operated within civil society and, at least in theory, expressed the interests of specific groups subordinate to the authorities. This was manifested in the activities of trade unions, environmental organisations and other entities representing collective interests.

The author pointed to a specific type of civic opposition, namely media opposition, distinguished not by the methods it used, but primarily by its social responsiveness, understood as the ability to articulate, disseminate and sometimes also create dominant opinions on the exercise of power. This opposition was formed by the mass media publishing critical content, sometimes of a decidedly confrontational nature, mainly towards the ruling groups, including their representatives and related circles. The mere fact of formulating critical assessments of those in power was not yet a sufficient basis for classifying a given medium as an opposition entity (Pałeczki, 2001, p. 18).

The author of this article shares the view presented by Tomasz Litwin, Krzysztof Łabędź and Mariusz Pękala, according to which not only the fact that the media took a critical stance towards those in power was of key importance, but also the nature and manner of their argumentation. These authors pointed out that balanced, multilateral and rational arguments based on scientific findings were, as a rule, unusual for media outlets classified as opposition media (Litwin et al., 2024, p. 15). They also pointed out an additional methodological difficulty, namely the dominance of messages with an unambiguously critical tone, which made it difficult to draw a precise distinction between journalistic criticism and opposition as a structural feature of the media. As a result, the classification of a given media outlet as part of the media opposition was largely discretionary, and the available criteria for such an assessment remained imprecise and undefined (Litwin et al., 2024, p. 15).

In light of the above considerations, it was necessary to clarify the meaning of the term used in the title of the article, i.e. media support, especially from the perspective of political science analysis. Media support should be understood as deliberate and systematic actions of the mass media which, through a specific selection of topics, choice of language, prioritisation of information, and the manner of presenting political actors, contributed to strengthening – indirectly, directly or institutionally – the position of specific political circles (e.g. the ruling party or the opposition).

It is worth emphasising that media support did not necessarily take the form of open agitation or explicit ideological declarations. It often manifested itself in non-obvious communication mechanisms, such as framing the message, reinforcing specific interpretative narratives, highlighting selected facts or information while marginalising others, or consistently building a positive or negative image of specific political actors (Michalczyk, 2020, p. 243; Maćkiewicz, 2020, pp. 621-622; Borkowski, 2018, pp. 153-154). For this reason, this phenomenon should be viewed as a long-term process of shaping social perception rather than as a collection of individual, easily identifiable messages (Wendt, 2007, pp. 56-57).

At the same time, assessing the existence of media support requires methodological caution, as the line between reliable journalistic commentary, critical analysis and the intentional reinforcement of specific political entities can be blurred and dependent on the research criteria adopted (Sobczak & Kakareko, 2022, p. 37). Therefore, this concept should be operationalised taking into account the content of messages, their context, frequency and consistency with the editorial line of a given medium.

PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS OF MEDIA CREDIBILITY AND POLITICAL ORIENTATION

Empirical research on the perception of the media in Poland indicates that citizens increasingly interpret media messages through the prism of political preferences. Surveys conducted by the Public Opinion Research Centre (CBOS) demonstrate that television and internet portals remain the most important sources of information about political events in Poland. In 2019, television was indicated as the main source of information by 58% of respondents, while the internet was mentioned by 27% of respondents (CBOS, 2017; 2019).

According to CBOS research conducted in 2023, television remains the primary source of information for half of Polish citizens (50%), while the internet has significantly strengthened its position and is now indicated by 40% of respondents. Radio (7%) and the press (1%) play a considerably smaller role in shaping public knowledge about current political events (CBOS, 2023).

The growing role of digital media is particularly visible among younger respondents, who rely primarily on internet sources when following political developments. In contrast, older generations remain strongly attached to television as the dominant

channel of political communication. This generational differentiation contributes to the fragmentation of the information environment and reinforces the diversification of political narratives circulating in the public sphere. At the same time, public opinion surveys reveal a growing perception of political bias among major broadcasters. According to CBOS research, more than half of respondents (54%) believed that programmes broadcast by TVN and TVN24 were favourable to the opposition, while 66% perceived public television as supporting the government (CBOS, 2019).

These perceptions correspond with broader patterns of media consumption related to political identity. Individuals identifying with right-wing political orientations more frequently rely on public television as their primary source of information, whereas respondents identifying with left-wing views more often rely on private broadcasters such as TVN or TVN24 (CBOS, 2021; 2023).

Such findings illustrate that the reception of media content in Poland is strongly conditioned by political identification and electoral preferences. In this context, the interpretation of media messages increasingly reflects the ideological alignment of audiences rather than the purely informational function of journalism.

The phenomenon described above corresponds with the concept of political parallelism, which refers to the alignment between media organisations and political actors or ideological camps. According to Daniel C. Hallin and Paolo Mancini (2004, pp. 26-27), political parallelism constitutes one of the fundamental characteristics of media systems in democratic societies, particularly in countries where political polarization is high and media outlets maintain clear ideological profiles (Dobek-Ostrowska, 2019, pp. 214-215; Newman et al., 2023).

In the Polish case, this phenomenon has intensified in the last decade due to several structural transformations of the media system. These include the expansion of digital platforms, the growing role of social media in political communication and the increasing fragmentation of audiences. As a result, citizens are more likely to consume information from media outlets that confirm their existing political beliefs, which contributes to the strengthening of partisan interpretations of political events (Hallin & Mancini, 2004, pp. 26-27).

Consequently, media institutions increasingly function not only as providers of information but also as actors participating in the broader dynamics of political competition. The perception that particular media outlets support specific political actors strengthens the role of the media as participants in political conflict and shapes public interpretations of political legitimacy and accountability.

An additional factor shaping contemporary political communication is the growing importance of digital platforms and social media, which have significantly transformed the structure of the public sphere. The increasing fragmentation of information flows and the algorithmic distribution of content have contributed to the intensification of political polarization and the formation of ideologically homogeneous information environments (CBOS, 2023). Research indicates that the role of the internet

as a primary source of political information has increased significantly in recent years. In 2023, 40% of Poles declared that the internet was their main source of information about current events, compared with 50% who relied on television. This transformation of the media ecosystem has strengthened the circulation of politically framed narratives and amplified conflicts between competing interpretations of political reality.

Despite the growing political polarization of the media environment, a majority of respondents still believe that the Polish media system remains pluralistic. According to CBOS surveys conducted in 2021, 65% of respondents considered the Polish media landscape to present diverse opinions and viewpoints, although this assessment varied significantly depending on political orientation and media consumption patterns (CBOS, 2021).

The importance of traditional media in shaping electoral attitudes remains substantial. During the parliamentary election campaign preceding the 2023 elections, 71% of respondents declared that they obtained information about candidates and political committees from television programmes, while 52% encountered such information online (CBOS, 2023). These data suggest that although digital media are gaining importance, television remains a key arena for political communication and agenda setting in Poland.

The analysis indicates that after 2015 the Polish media system became increasingly embedded in the dynamics of political conflict. In such conditions, certain media outlets began to function not only as observers or commentators on political processes but also as actors participating in the broader struggle for political influence. This phenomenon should not be interpreted solely as the result of political pressure or institutional changes within public media. It is also connected with deeper structural transformations of the media ecosystem, including digitalization, the growing importance of social media platforms and the increasing polarization of audiences.

THE GENERAL POLITICAL SITUATION IN POLAND AFTER 2015 – A BRIEF OVERVIEW

The change of government that took place in 2015 was twofold. Firstly, in the presidential elections held on 10 May (first round) and 24 May (second round) 2015, the incumbent President Bronisław Komorowski, supported by the Civic Platform (PO), the Democratic Party *demokracy.pl* (successor to the Freedom Union), the Green Party of the Republic of Poland and the Democratic Party, lost to Andrzej Duda, the candidate of Law and Justice (PiS), supported by Zbigniew Ziobro's *Solidarna Polska* (SPZZ), Jarosław Gowin's *Polska Razem* (PRJG), the League for the Defence of Sovereignty, the „Piast” Party, and the national committee of the „Solidarity” movement. Then, in the 2020 presidential election, Duda repeated his success, successfully running for re-election and defeating Rafał Trzaskowski (PO).

Secondly, as a result of the parliamentary elections of 25 October 2015, the previous coalition of the Civic Platform and the Polish People's Party (PSL) lost power after eight years of rule to a broad camp commonly referred to as the United Right (ZP), whose organisational and programmatic core remained PiS. Its members included representatives of the SPZZ and PRJG (Wicherek, 2017, pp. 45-49). As a result, out of 460 seats in the Sejm, ZP won 235 seats, PO – 138, KWW Kukiz'15 – 42, Ryszard Petru's Nowoczesna – 28, PSL – 16, and one seat went to the German Minority. For the first time, the left wing found itself outside parliament. ZP was also successful in the Senate elections, where it won 61 seats. The remaining seats went to PO (34), PSL (1), and another 4 seats to independent candidates (PKW, 2019).

What distinguished the 2015 parliamentary elections was a precedent-setting situation, as since the political transformation in Poland, one electoral committee had obtained an independent majority in the Sejm, enabling it to form a government on its own (Dudek, 2023, p. 617). However, researchers studying this phenomenon were divided on the issue of independence, as pointed out by Joanna Kozierska, among others, who believed that the government formed after the parliamentary elections clearly bore the hallmarks of a coalition government rather than a single-party government, mainly due to the non-coalition list of the Law and Justice party (Kozierska, 2022, p. 157).

On the basis of these electoral successes, the ZP, actively supported by the government-affiliated media, won again in the next parliamentary elections, which took place on 13 October 2019. As a result, the ZP retained its previous number of MPs, i.e. 235. The Civic Coalition (PO, Nowoczesna and Zieloni) won 138 seats, the Democratic Left Alliance (SLD) exceeded the required electoral threshold this time and won 46 seats in the Sejm, the PSL won 30 seats, and the Confederation of Freedom and Independence won 11 seats. One seat went to the German Minority. At the same time, the position of the ZP in the Polish Senate weakened, with 48 seats, KO - 43, PSL - 3, SLD - 2, and 4 seats going to independent candidates (PKW, 2019). This resulted in a slight advantage for the opposition parties in the Polish Senate, following the signing of the so-called Senate pact (Kuźniarski, 2024, pp. 21-22).

The aforementioned change of government in 2015 led to a clear shift in both the function and role of public media in Poland. Instead of fulfilling their traditional mission of providing diverse information, journalism, cultural, educational and entertainment content, these media began to increasingly serve as active tools for political communication by the ruling camp. This phenomenon was multidimensional, as it encompassed both the content of the message, editorial practices and the institutional conditions for the functioning of the media (Łabędź, 2023, pp. 112-117).

The government could count on the support of a wide range of media outlets, in particular Telewizja Polska (Polish Television), especially its main news programme „Wiadomości”, as well as TVP1 and TVP3 channels, TV Republika, Telewizja Trwam and Radio Maryja, Polish Radio (especially 1st channel - Program Pierwszy and 3rd channel - Program Trzeci), the opinion weeklies Sieci, „Do Rzeczy” and „Gazeta Polska”,

the daily „Gazeta Polska Codziennie”, and the wPolityce.pl portal. Another important element of this arrangement was the acquisition by Orlen of the Polska Press group, comprising 20 regional dailies, around 150 local weeklies and an extensive network of internet portals, which has reduced media pluralism at the local level (Paczeński, 2024, p. 152.).

Empirical confirmation of the pro-government nature of public media coverage was provided, among others, by research conducted by Rafał Klepka (2025, p. 278), Wojciech Kułaga and Wojciech Maguś, who showed that after 2015, Telewizja Polska presented a clearly biased and positive image of the political reality. An analysis of the content of news programmes indicated that government decisions were presented as the implementation of the „will of the people” (Klepka et al., 2025, p. 43). This was accompanied by specific communication strategies, such as selective topic selection, biased framing of messages, preference for specific (so-called pro-government) experts and commentators (rather than scientists), as well as strong political narrative (Dopierała & Ossowski, 2018, p. 13; Ossowski & Kendzior, 2023, p. 190). In turn, the parliamentary opposition was presented as a source of destabilisation and chaos, incompetent, internally divided or acting against the national interest, which contributed to its delegitimisation as a full participant in public debate.

Furthermore, during the ZP government’s term, changes took place in the landscape of public and private media. These consisted of the introduction of an advertising tax, and the government’s influence on the media was also strengthened as a result of the establishment of the National Media Council on 22 June 2016. The „good change” also affected journalists, both in traditional media (television, press) and online media, where editorial positions were filled by people associated with the ruling camp¹.

Numerous attempts were made to repolonise the media and restrict their freedom by amending the Broadcasting Act, which aimed to introduce a 49% limit on foreign capital in media entities operating in the Republic of Poland. In practice, this applied in particular to the TVN broadcaster, owned by the American company Discovery (commonly referred to as the „Lex TVN” act) (Stasiak-Jazukiewicz, 2023, pp. 119-150). However, this law did not come into force due to President A. Duda’s veto (Wicherek, 2025, p. 400-405).

The above actions meant that this support was not only editorial in nature, but was also systematically reinforced. The influence of the government, presented here only in brief, meant that the media favourable to the authorities significantly influenced public perception of the most important political events in the country and of the politicians

1 According to the Journalists’ Association, approximately 200 people lost their jobs in the media by October 2016 alone. See Piotr Zieliński (2016). Cicha zmiana, *Press*, 10, p. 54.

themselves (both the government and the opposition). As a result of this process, the audience received a clearly polarised message, which made it much more difficult to create a neutral and common space for public debate.

MEDIA SUPPORT FOR THE PARLIAMENTARY OPPOSITION

Parallel to the aforementioned strengthening of the media segment favourable to the ruling camp after 2015, there was also an extensive media trend in the Polish media space which, it must be admitted, provided varying degrees of support for both the parliamentary opposition at the time and its narrative. These media outlets, remaining in opposition to both the ruling party and the pro-government media, took on a critical role towards the authorities. At the same time, they performed the classic function of the media as the „fourth estate” (Litwin et al., 2024, pp. 28-29).

The polarisation of the media system after 2015 was evident, among other things, in the asymmetrical selection of topics and experts and in the different ways of framing the same events (Hallin & Mancini, 2021, pp. 190-206). One example is the crisis surrounding the Constitutional Tribunal (2015–2016), which was consistently portrayed in the opposition-friendly media as a violation of the principle of the separation of powers, while the pro-government media interpreted it as a „restoration of constitutional order” (Dopierała & Ossowski, 2018, pp. 14-15). A similar mechanism was observed in the coverage of social protests (e.g. the Black Protest in 2016 or the protests in defence of the courts in 2017), where the opposition media emphasised the civic and grassroots nature of the mobilisation, while the pro-government media emphasised its externally inspired origins (Adamczyk, 2021, pp. 14-21).

Among the media entities that played a key role in the polarised media landscape, TVN and TVN24 television stations were particularly important. Current affairs and news programmes such as „Kropka nad i”, „Fakty po Faktach” and investigative reports produced by the „Superwizjer” editorial team consistently addressed controversial government decisions, including political scandals, numerous abuses of power and violations of democratic standards. The investigative journalism present in these formats not only provided the public with information that did not appear in the public media, but also contributed to the consolidation of a critical narrative towards the ruling party, which strengthened the position of the opposition as a political actor capable of articulating an alternative vision of the state (Polińska, 2022, p. 212).

The journalistic activities of TVN and TVN24 have repeatedly initiated a series of successive political impacts, confirming their agenda-setting function. One example is the series of reports by „Superwizjer” on the activities of neo-Nazi circles in 2018, which led to a reaction from the public prosecutor’s office and a parliamentary debate. Similarly, reports on the KNF scandal and the so-called „email scandal” of 2021 were initially present mainly in the commercial media and then taken up by opposition politicians as part of their criticism of the government (Towarzystwo Dziennikarskie, 2021).

Radio TOK FM served a similar function, with programming based on extensive journalistic broadcasts, numerous expert analyses and political commentary. By frequently inviting representatives of opposition circles, independent experts and critics of the government, these programmes created a broad space for debate that was much more pluralistic than what was available in the public media at the time. TOK FM thus became one of the key forums for liberal-democratic discourse after 2015 (Sojak et al., 2023 ; Klepka et al., 2025, pp. 309-311).

TOK FM programmes such as „Poranek Radia TOK FM” (TOK FM Morning) and „Komentarze” (Comments) regularly invited constitutional experts (e.g. Ewa Łętowska, Marek Safjan, Wojciech Sadurski) to interpret legislative changes in the context of European standards. During the judicial reform period in 2017-2018, this medium acted as an intermediary in the transfer of knowledge, simplifying complex legal issues and adapting them to the audience’s level of perception, which helped to strengthen the opposition narrative in the public debate (Szukała, 2025; Sitnicka, 2023).

Table 1. Characteristics of media discourse in Poland during the United Right government

No.	Key elements of media narrative	Media supporting the opposition
1	attitude towards the government	critical; the government was portrayed as a threat to democracy, the rule of law and civil liberties
2	attitude towards the opposition	positive and neutral; the opposition was presented as an alternative to the ZP government and, as a result of being marginalised in the government-dominated media, enjoyed privileged status (it was presented much more often)
3	dominant topics in the media	exposing scandals and abuses by those in power; violating the constitution and the rule of law; restricting civil rights and freedoms; restricting the independence of courts and judges; promoting social protests
4	language and style of communication	emotional; often confrontational; words used: „guardians of democracy”, „defenders of order”, „democratic forces”
5	attitude towards the Catholic Church	critical of abuses by the Church and its representatives; promoting the separation of Church and state; frequently addressing the issue of paedophilia in the Church and its victims

6	potential threats (enemies)	„party state”; „repression of independent institutions”; „Kaczynism”; „authoritarianism”; threat to free media, state institutions and elections
7	attitude towards protesters	supporting and promoting protests; these were treated as an expression of civil opposition to violations of democracy and constitutional values
8	most frequently presented slogans	„Constitution”; „free courts”; „free media”; „rule of law”; „democratic Poland, not authoritarian Poland”.

Source: own study based on: *Media Freedom at a Crossroads: Journalism in Poland faces uncertain future ahead of election. Mission Report on media capture and vexatious lawsuits in Poland by the Media Freedom Rapid Response*, https://www.mfrr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Poland-media-freedom-at-a-crossroads.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com, [access: 13.01.2026]; *Rzeczypospolita Polska. Wybory parlamentarne 13 października 2019 . Krótkoterminowa misja obserwacji wyborów ODIHR. Sprawozdanie końcowe*, <https://www.osce.org/sites/default/files/f/documents/8/8/448417.pdf>, [access: 14.01.2026]; *Republic of Poland. Parliamentary election 15 October 2023. ODIHR Limited Election Observation Mission Final Report*, https://www.sn.pl/sites/Serwis_WWW/SiteAssets/Lists/Wydarzenia/AllItems/Raport%20ODIHR%20wybory%202023.pdf, [access: 14.01.2026]; *Raport Komisji ds. wyjaśnienia mechanizmów represji wobec organizacji społeczeństwa obywatelskiego oraz działaczy społecznych w latach 2015-2023*, <https://www.gov.pl/web/sprawiedliwosc/prezentacja-pierwszego-raportu-komisji-ds-represji-wobec-spolnoczenia-obywatelskiego-w-mediach-publicznych-2015-2023>, [access: 14.01.2026].

The press and online portals also played an important role in providing media support to the opposition. „Gazeta Wyborcza”, together with the Gazeta.pl website, consistently took a critical stance towards the government, publishing both editorial comments and investigative reports on abuses of power. „Gazeta Wyborcza” ran long-term thematic series, including on the politicisation of state-owned companies, the relationship between the government and the Church, and the mechanisms of election campaign financing. „Newsweek Polska” played a similar role, functioning under the editorial leadership of Tomasz Lis as one of the main media outlets narratively favourable to the liberal opposition (Litwin et. al., 2024, pp. 51-56). An example of this was a series of covers and reports on personal connections within the ruling camp. Such materials were later repeatedly cited in opposition election campaigns as evidence of systemic abuses.

Digital media outlets such as OKO.press, which specialises in analytical journalism, also deserve special attention. This portal served a function similar to that of social control, verifying the messages of the authorities and public media, and thus providing the opposition with substantive arguments and tools for criticism. OKO.press

regularly published analyses as part of the „Sprawdzamy” (We Check) series, verifying statements made by the prime minister and ministers, which were then disseminated on social media by opposition politicians.

Onet.pl, on the other hand, thanks to its wide reach, effectively publicised issues such as nepotism in the administration and controversial personnel appointments, which led to their consolidation in the public debate. Through its wide reach and appropriate exposure of materials critical of the government, this portal had a real impact on the public debate agenda.

The role of intellectual and ideological circles associated with Krytyka Polityczna, which combined media activity with expert and academic work, cannot be overlooked either. Although these media outlets had a clear ideological profile, they provided interpretations of socio-political processes that were alternative to the government narrative. Social (civic) communication also gained in importance, with movements such as Akcja Demokracja (Democracy Action), the All-Poland Women’s Strike and Citizens of the Republic of Poland, which used popular social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter/X, YouTube and Instagram) to build a grassroots community of opposition to the authorities, organise protests and frequently publicise controversial government decisions (CBOS, 2016; 2020). Social media ceased to be merely a channel of communication, as during the ZP government it became a powerful tool for political mobilisation, particularly evident during hundreds of mass social protests after 2016 (Wiącek, 2021, pp. 23-24).

Based on an analysis of reports on the media in Poland, selected examples of the leading elements of media narrative supporting the parliamentary opposition after 2015 have been compiled (Table 1). The examples of media support for the parliamentary opposition listed above were, of course, not the only ones that appeared in the political arena. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that this support comprehensively covered traditional media, opinion-forming media, digital media, social media platforms and civic initiatives. Although they did not form a unified ideological bloc, they were ultimately united by a common function of creating an alternative space for public debate and a specific media narrative, while enabling the parliamentary opposition to function effectively in the sphere of political communication. All this took place in opposition to the dominant message of the ruling camp.

SUMMARY

The analysis conducted in this article sought to answer the question of why and in what ways selected media outlets in Poland after 2015 increasingly assumed the role of actors supporting the parliamentary opposition within the process of political communication. Rather than verifying a strictly formulated hypothesis, the study focused on identifying the mechanisms through which media narratives contributed to strengthening the visibility and legitimacy of opposition actors in the public sphere.

The findings indicate that several factors shaped this process. First, the transformation of the Polish media system, including the growing role of digital platforms and social media, intensified the circulation of politically framed narratives and contributed to the fragmentation of the information environment. Second, the analysis revealed the importance of discursive strategies and framing techniques used in media coverage, which frequently emphasized conflict, criticism of government actions and the legitimacy of opposition actors as interpreters of political developments.

At the same time, empirical data on public perceptions of the media suggest that the reception of media content in Poland is strongly influenced by political identification and ideological preferences. As a result, media outlets increasingly operate within a polarized communication environment in which audiences interpret information through the prism of political affiliation.

In this context, selected media outlets cannot be understood solely as neutral transmitters of information. Instead, they function as actors participating in the broader dynamics of political competition and the symbolic construction of political conflict.

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MEDIALNE WSPARCIE OPOZYCJI PARLAMENTARNEJ W POLSCE PO 2015 ROKU: WYBRANE PRZYKŁADY

ABSTRAKT

Analiza dotyczyła zjawiska wsparcia medialnego dla opozycji parlamentarnej w Polsce po 2015 roku, umieszczając je w szerszym kontekście zmian w systemie medialnym oraz polaryzacji politycznej. Podjęte rozważania odnoszą się do klasycznego rozumienia roli mediów jako czwartej władzy w demokracji, ze szczególnym uwzględnieniem znaczenia ich niezależności, pluralizmu oraz odpowiedzialności dziennikarskiej jako warunków prawidłowego funkcjonowania sfery publicznej. Jednocześnie wskazuje się, że po 2015 roku, w wyniku zmiany władzy, nastąpiło istotne przesunięcie funkcji zarówno mediów publicznych, jak i prywatnych w kierunku zaangażowania politycznego, co osłabiło ich neutralność i dodatkowo pogłębiło podziały społeczne.

Słowa kluczowe: *opozycja parlamentarna, media, Polska, Zjednoczona Prawica, narracje medialne*

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Doktor nauk humanistycznych w zakresie nauk o polityce. Specjalizuje się w szeroko rozumianej problematyce współczesnych partii politycznych. Obecnie prowadzi badania nad kondycją opozycji parlamentarnej oraz możliwością adaptacji westminsterskiego modelu partii opozycyjnych („gabinet cieni”) w Polsce, na Słowacji, Litwie i we Włoszech. E-mail: dszczepanski@ur.edu.pl.